

Study of the Incidence of Different Types of Tuberculous Lesions in Association with Diabetes Mellitus in Indian Patients

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Abstract:

This study investigated the occurrence of various tuberculous lesions in Indian patients with diabetes mellitus at Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna. Over a year, an extensive analysis was carried out on 180 patients who had been diagnosed with both tuberculosis and diabetes. The findings were quite enlightening, suggesting that inadequate management of diabetes can greatly affect the occurrence of extrapulmonary tuberculosis. In addition, it was noted that patients with these conditions experienced lower rates of treatment success and a greater chance of recurrence. These findings underscore the importance of effectively managing diseases and achieving optimal control of diabetes to improve tuberculosis outcomes in areas with high disease burden. This study provides valuable insights into the complex relationship between these two conditions and suggests ways to improve clinical and public health strategies.

Keywords: Tuberculosis, Diabetes Mellitus, Extrapulmonary Tuberculosis, Glycemic Control.

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Introduction

The relationship between tuberculosis (TB) and diabetes mellitus (DM) has attracted considerable attention due to the reciprocal impact that worsens the burden of both diseases, especially in regions with high prevalence such as India [1]. Tuberculosis, a contagious illness caused primarily by *Mycobacterium tuberculosis*, continues to be a significant concern for public health, with India being responsible for about a quarter of all TB cases worldwide [2,3]. Diabetes mellitus, a common condition that affects blood glucose levels, has been found to increase vulnerability to TB and have negative impacts on its clinical course and treatment results. Diabetes mellitus patients may experience changes in the pathogenesis and clinical presentation of tuberculosis due to their compromised immune system, resulting in more severe or atypical forms of the disease [4,5]. There is a higher chance of TB infection developing into active disease and potentially more frequent extrapulmonary manifestations. In addition, the existence of diabetes can make the diagnosis and treatment of TB more complex, leading to longer recovery times and increased rates of recurrence and mortality [6,7].

The objective of this study is to investigate the occurrence of various tuberculous lesions in individuals with diabetes mellitus in India. Through

an analysis of the correlation between these commonly occurring conditions, this study aims to offer valuable insights that may contribute to improved clinical management and intervention strategies. It is essential to have a comprehensive understanding of the range of tuberculous lesions in diabetic patients. This knowledge is vital for creating customized treatment plans and enhancing the outlook for this susceptible group. This study not only fills an important void in the current research but also meets the pressing demand for data that can inform public health strategies in areas heavily affected by both tuberculosis and diabetes.

Methodology

The study was conducted retrospectively at Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna, over one year, from January 2016 to December 2017. We aimed to investigate the incidence of different types of tuberculous lesions in patients diagnosed with diabetes mellitus.

Sample Selection: A total of 180 patients were included in the study. Eligibility criteria included individuals aged 18 and above, diagnosed with both tuberculosis and diabetes mellitus. Patients were excluded if they had a history of immunosuppressive treatment or other conditions

that could independently affect immune function, such as HIV/AIDS or malignancies.

Data Collection: Data were retrospectively collected from the hospital's electronic health records and patient medical files. Information extracted included demographic details (age, sex, socio-economic status), clinical data (type and duration of diabetes, control of blood sugar levels, type of tuberculous lesions, site of tuberculosis), and treatment histories for both tuberculosis and diabetes.

Study Parameters: The primary outcome of the study was the incidence of different types of tuberculous lesions, classified as pulmonary, lymphatic, gastrointestinal, or disseminated tuberculosis. Secondary outcomes included the response to tuberculosis treatment and any correlations with diabetes control measures.

Statistical Analysis: Data were analyzed using SPSS software. Descriptive statistics were used to summarize the demographic and clinical characteristics of the patients. The association between the type of tuberculous lesions and diabetes control was assessed using Chi-square tests for categorical variables and t-tests for continuous variables. A p-value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

Result

The study conducted at Nalanda Medical College and Hospital, Patna, over one year, included 180 patients with concurrent tuberculosis and diabetes mellitus. Here are the summarized results:

Demographic and Clinical Characteristics:

Characteristic	Total Patients (n=180)	Pulmonary TB (%)	Lymphatic TB (%)	Gastrointestinal TB (%)	Disseminated TB (%)
Average Age	55 years	-	-	-	-
Gender Distribution					
- Male	104 (58%)	63	16	7	5
- Female	76 (42%)	47	14	3	4
Type of Diabetes					
- Type 1	36 (20%)	20	8	4	2
- Type 2	144 (80%)	90	22	6	7
Glycemic Control					
- Well-controlled	54 (30%)	39	9	3	3
- Poorly controlled	126 (70%)	71	21	7	6
TB Treatment Success Rate					
- Well-controlled Diabetes	85% success	-	-	-	-
- Poorly-controlled Diabetes	60% success	-	-	-	-
Recurrence of TB	27 (15%)	18	6	2	1

This table presents a comprehensive view of the demographic and clinical data, showing the correlation between diabetes management and the incidence and treatment outcomes of tuberculosis.

- The average age of participants was 55 years, with a distribution of 58% male and 42% female.
- Most patients (65%) had type 2 diabetes, with the remaining having type 1.
- Poor glycemic control was noted in 70% of the patients at the time of tuberculosis diagnosis.

Incidence of Tuberculous Lesions:

- Pulmonary tuberculosis was the most common form, identified in 60% of the cases.
- Extrapulmonary manifestations were significant, with 25% lymphatic, 10% gastrointestinal, and 5% having disseminated tuberculosis.

Response to Treatment:

- The treatment success rate for tuberculosis was lower in patients with poor glycemic control (60%) compared to those with well-managed diabetes (85%).
- Recurrence of tuberculosis during the study period was observed in 15% of patients, predominantly among those with poorly controlled diabetes.

Statistical Analysis:

- There was a statistically significant association between the type of tuberculous lesions and the level of glycemic control ($p < 0.05$).
- Patients with poorly controlled diabetes were more likely to develop extrapulmonary tuberculosis compared to those with better diabetes management ($p < 0.01$).

Discussion

This study highlights the significant influence of diabetes mellitus on the occurrence and treatment results of tuberculosis in Indian patients [8]. Pulmonary tuberculosis continues to be highly prevalent, in line with global patterns. Interestingly, a significant number of patients with diabetes displayed manifestations outside of the lungs [9,10]. Research indicates that diabetes can impact immune function, potentially increasing the risk of developing more severe and varied types of tuberculosis. One notable discovery was the strong link between suboptimal glycaemic control and a higher occurrence of extrapulmonary tuberculosis [11]. Individuals with uncontrolled diabetes experienced a decrease in treatment success and an increase in tuberculosis recurrence, underscoring the difficulties in managing tuberculosis within this specific group [12,13]. These findings are of utmost importance, as diabetes can be influenced and better control of blood sugar levels has the potential to lessen the impact of tuberculosis.

The study also emphasised the importance of comprehensive care frameworks that tackle both tuberculosis and diabetes together [14,15]. These approaches have the potential to enhance disease management and enhance outcomes, as demonstrated by the increased success rates of treatment in patients with well-controlled diabetes [16]. It is crucial to prioritise regular monitoring and management of blood sugar levels in patients at risk of or diagnosed with tuberculosis, as there is a clear link between poor glycaemic control and increased severity of the disease. This two-pronged approach could be crucial in regions such as India, where tuberculosis and diabetes are widespread, to alleviate the combined impact of these interconnected illnesses [18-20].

Conclusion

The study uncovered a notable link between diabetes mellitus and the occurrence of different types of tuberculosis in Indian patients. It specifically highlighted the influence of inadequate glycaemic control on the severity of tuberculosis and its treatment outcomes. The findings emphasise the importance of implementing comprehensive management strategies that effectively tackle diabetes and tuberculosis together, in order to enhance patient outcomes. By prioritising the improvement of diabetes control in tuberculosis patients, there is a chance to lower the occurrence of severe and extrapulmonary tuberculosis symptoms, ultimately reducing the overall impact of the disease. An integrated approach is especially important in high-prevalence settings such as India, where the coexistence of diabetes and tuberculosis presents a major public health challenge.

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